

Disaster Risk Reduction Education: Assessing School Safety Towards Haze Pollution in Indonesia

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Abstract: Haze has become a perennial event in several provinces of Indonesia and neighbouring countries over the last several decades. This air pollution-type hazard is mostly caused by forest fires and wildfires from peatland areas which are also the greatest source of carbon emissions within the region. Vulnerable groups have been impacted by this haze hazard including millions of school children. Therefore, this study aims to assess school safety in regards to exposure to haze pollution within Indonesian school settings. The assessment is based on the three school safety pillars on the globally adopted Comprehensive School Safety Framework (CSS) which include Pillar 1: Safe Learning Facilities, Pillar 2: School Disaster Management and Pillar 3: Risk Reduction and Resilience Education. A mixed-method is applied to analyse the data collected from experts' interview and teachers' survey on the six affected provinces. The result reveals that the school safety readiness in Indonesia varies among the three pillars. Pillar 1 has been assessed as the least progressive in which the majority of school infrastructures in Indonesia are not prepared to cope with disaster risks, particularly haze. The obstacles vary from lack of disaster safety standards to a lack of policy implementation and monitoring. Meanwhile, Pillar 2 and Pillar 3 have shown more progress sustained by the improved multi-stakeholder partnerships and the flexibility of the national curriculum. Recommendations to accelerate the safe school provisions in relation to haze, among other hazards, include; strengthening the capability of school leadership, ensuring the commitment of local political leaders and systematically incorporating Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) education learning for school communities.

Keywords: haze pollution, school safety, local leaders, disaster safety standards

1. Introduction

Haze pollution is one type of air pollution hazard which is caused by numerous factors, including unintentional wildfires, intentional forest fires, intentional peatland fires, industrial waste, and transportation fumes. In Indonesia, the haze crisis has become a seasonal event that usually takes place in the dry season – around May to October depending on the conditions – and spreads across peatland areas (Gaveau et al., 2014). Peatland fires are considered more dangerous than other types of haze pollution events, because they can produce more smoke particles in the air per unit volume. Peat areas can be as deep as 10m underground containing organic layers Hu et al., (2018), and these layers can burn for weeks after the surface fire has gone (Roulston et al., 2018).

Haze is a long-term phenomenon that occurs almost every year in the country with variations of scale, but the most notable haze events occurred in the years 1982–1983, 1997–1998, 2006, 2009, 2013, 2015 and 2019 (Kiely et al., 2019). In the past, fires were often times driven by ENSO (El-Nino Southern Oscillation) conditions, however, recently they have also been worsened by the effects of climate change. Thus, haze pollution has been recognised as a regular hazard blanketing the regions where fires are found or are adjacent to, such as in South Sumatra, Jambi, Riau, West and Central Kalimantan as well as regions in neighbouring countries (regions of Malaysia and Singapore) (Bisri, 2019). These haze event have been happening for a long time and continue affecting more and more people throughout each decade. Although there are millions of people exposed to the perennial blanketing smoke, unlike other popular hazards, haze events seem to be under researched. Moreover, while fire hazards that cause haze pollution were recently recognised as one of the global risks in the Sendai Framework of 2015, up to date, information regarding this disaster risk has just started to grow, despite of it has already and continuously brought devastating consequences for millions of lives around the world for decades (UNDRR, 2019).

There are few signs that the situation is improving in the South East Asia context. A joint-effort to tackle the haze pollution problem called the 2002 ASEAN Agreement on Trans-boundary Haze Pollution (AATHP) has only been ratified by some member states, with Indonesia as the major contributor of the problems signing the agreement already 12 years after its establishment (Kamaruddin & Marwan, 2018). This indicates that even though the recent media attention on globally distributed wildfires may have raised awareness of the issue in global communities, there are gaps in both policy and research on what can be done about the problem that need to be investigated further.

The risks from haze hazards, additionally, cannot be undermined particularly over a long period of time. One of the reasons for concern is because the increment in Pollutant Standard Index (PSI) is significantly associated with an increased risk of mortality over a lifetime (Ho et. al., 2019) – meaning the students exposed to haze are risking their lives while studying in schools during haze periods in their younger years. The study in 2018 by Hanafi et al., (2018) found that the Upper Respiratory Tract Infection (URTI) cases were directly related to particulate matters (PM) concentration and air pollution index (API) values. This research also reveals that during the haze periods, there are many more people affected by respiratory health issues than in periods without haze pollution. Furthermore, Sharma & Balasubramanian (2018) emphasise that higher intensity during haze events causes the health risk to increase as well.

They also suggest that staying indoor with a naturally ventilated environment is not safe – urging indoor mitigation efforts such as utilising suitable portable air cleaners. This seems to be critical in dealing with the health risk considering that the increment of Pollution Standard Index (PSI) was significantly associated with an increased mortality rate (Ho et al., 2019).

Moreover, haze exacerbate various respiratory infections and other chronic circulatory diseases. The World Health Organization (WHO) identifies that every year both outdoor and indoor air pollution has been the cause of approximately seven million premature deaths, in which the most cases are due to increased mortality from various illness such as acute respiratory infections, stroke, heart disease, and lung cancer with the most vulnerable groups being older generations and children (WHO, 2020). However, for younger generations – even though most of their time is spent at schools – they have lower awareness or the hazards of haze pollution compared to older adults (Acreman et al., 2015). In Indonesia alone, there are 26,503 schools with more than five million total students across all levels of education who were affected at the peak of a recent haze period (Bisri, 2019).

Nevertheless, despite of the haze pollution impacts that extremely threaten school aged children, progress on research concerning disaster risk reduction and education is not promising. Globally, integration of disaster risk reduction and disaster response into the education sector policy in most countries is not very prevalent, putting school communities, especially those in developing countries, at greater risk and making them more vulnerable (Amri A., et al., 2017; Sheffield et al., 2017). Moreover, in Indonesia, Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) education has been more practiced at the higher education level, but less practiced at the primary and secondary education levels (Suppasari et al., 2015). This may indicate that there have been limited efforts in reducing the risks for lower grades school children as one of the most vulnerable groups during haze pollution events. Therefore, this research aims to contribute in exploring the actual condition of school safety in Indonesia, particularly towards the relatively underrated haze pollution hazard by assessing the reality of policy implementation and teachers' perception within the haze affected regions. This study specifically aims: (i) to assess the current state of three school safety pillars in reducing the risks of haze pollution in Indonesia and (ii) to investigate the opportunities and challenges in risk reduction and resilience education towards haze pollution hazard in Indonesia.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Mixed Methodology

A combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches was optimised for the methodology in this study. The mixed methods approach in education research is efficient because it comprehends a clear and strategic relationship among the methods in order to triangulate the data, resulting in more in-depth insights than a singular approach can do (Lingard et al., 2008). The study employed semi-structured interviews and questionnaire surveys. In order to achieve the research objectives, this study applied both non-probability and probability sampling techniques to collect the data. For the probability sampling, a cluster technique was utilised to select the limit of the study areas. Cluster sampling means there are clusters or groups resulted from dividing the whole population (Taherdoost, 2016). And then, the final samples were randomly selected from these groups or clusters (Wilson, 2010). For the

non-probability sampling employed in this study, snowballing will be used for interviewing key informants from IGOs, NGOs, disaster agencies, and academia. It is hoped that by asking references from related institutes, diverse relevant insights and perspectives can be obtained.

2.2 Study Area

According to Bisri (2019), there were five provinces in Indonesia severely affected by haze in the 2019 – which was considered as the most recent major haze events. These regions are South Sumatra, Jambi, Riau, Central Kalimantan, West Kalimantan and small part of South Kalimantan (Figure 1). By considering that the regions mentioned above were severely affected in the latest massive haze event in 2019, those areas have been clustered as the main location for this study. Though differences emerge in terms of the level of haze concentration, generally, all provinces were affected by moderate haze pollution, and only a smaller part of the region was covered by extremely dense haze. Some of the areas that experienced dense air pollution was South Sumatra, Jambi, and Riau including where their respective capital cities are situated. Therefore, in the data collection process, though questionnaires were spread to teachers across the five provinces, this research might be more relevant to teachers and school community in those regions which experienced the most severe haze hazard.

Figure 1. Study locations for collecting survey data: South Sumatra, Jambi and Riau are among the most impacted regions by transboundary haze

2.3 Data Collection

2.3.1 Semi-structured interview

The primary data sources for this study took the form of semi-structured interviews and questionnaires. First, a semi-structured approach was selected for interviews, where a predetermined set of questions were asked and the researcher was free to seek clarification or

add more questions as deemed relevant (Doody, 2013). In order to create a sense of order during the interview, an interview guide was also developed based on the contexts of the study. The questions were open-ended, and consisted of a maximum of 10 questions to be answered. The development of these questions was guided by the extensive literature review, particularly on the relevant frameworks utilised in school safety research (Kitamura, 2014; GADRRRES, 2017; Sheffield et al., 2017; Shricai et al., 2013). The approximate time for the interview was about 45 minutes, varied depending on the situational responses of the interviewee. During the interview, the audio was recorded after getting the permission from interviewees. This was necessary to help in writing the transcript before analysis, because there was a language difference where the report was written in English, but the interview was in Bahasa Indonesia.

The initial plan was to conduct onsite interviews involving as many as experts following the snowball sampling, however, due to Covid-19 pandemic, online interviews were arranged. As for the final interviewees, there were six experts were interviewed, comprised of three practitioners with the experiences working with various organisations such as NGO, IGO, academic think tank, national government and universities in Indonesia (Table 1). In order to make the discussion more organised and transparent, the respective experts will be coded with initials, such as **G** for the person represents government agency, **P** for representatives from practitioners, and **A** for academics. The discussion transcripts acquired from the online semi-structured interview were extracted, and information regarding the expertise and experience of the informants concerning school safety issues in Indonesia covering all three school safety pillars were discussed after coding processes was completed.

Table 1. Code and Profile of the Interviewees

Code	Type of Institute/Organisation	Gender	Role
Government Agency (G)			
G1	Governmental Body	Male	Officer in the National Secretariat of Disaster Safety Education Unit (SPAB)
Professional Practitioners (P)			
P1	Inter-governmental Organisation	Male	National Professional Officer for Disaster Risk Reduction
P2	Academic Think-tank	Male	Practitioner with more than 10 years' experience in DRR and school safety; school safety national consultants for various IGOs
P3	Non-Governmental Organisation	Female	DRR specialist with more than 15 years' experience mostly in NGOs
Academics (A)			
A1	University	Female	Lecturer and the Coordinator for Disaster Education and Management Research Cluster at Tsunami and Disaster Mitigation Research Centre (TDMRC)
A2	University	Male	Lecturer and Head of Curriculum Directorate

2.3.2 Questionnaire Survey

Online surveys were delivered to teachers that reside on five different regions within Indonesia based on the severe haze impacted areas in 2019 (South Sumatra, Jambi, Riau, West Kalimantan and Central Kalimantan). The online survey contains 30 core questions in total which are divided into three big themes based on the three pillars of school safety: safe learning facilities, school disaster management, as well as resilience and risk reduction education – also

guided by the relevant frameworks on previous studies (Kitamura, 2014; GADRRRES, 2017; Sheffield et al., 2017; Shricai et al., 2013). On each theme, five questions were presented using a Likert Scale type in which respondents can choose one option ranging from the most contrary (also labelled as 1) to the most agreeable (labelled as 5). Example for the option ranges include Fully Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neither Disagree nor Agree (3), Agree (4), and Fully Agree (5). The other five questions for each of the three themes were closed ended multiple choices. The formulated questionnaires were put in a Google Form format to make them more accessible to deliver online. The finalised version of the questionnaire can be accessed through the link (tiny.cc/sekolah-kabutasap) where it was easily distributed to the targeted teachers via social media, namely WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, and E-Mail. Initially, the total questions were 15 on each theme, comprised of 45 questions in total, plus there were five additional open-ended questions. However, based on feedback from the initial trial for the questionnaire that was done with five teachers from Jambi, South Sumatra, and Riau provinces, the total number of questions was reduced to 30 and there were no open-ended questions as they made the process too lengthy, thus causing ineffective responses.

2.4 Data Analysis

2.4.1 Content Analysis

In this study, content analysis was utilised to analyse interview data because it provides in-depth contextualisation in answering the objectives of the study. Content analysis can be defined as a technique that is able to make replicable and valid finding from texts or other forms to contexts of their use (Krippendorff, 2004 in Bengtsson, 2016). The content analysis comprises several steps within the process. According to Bengtsson (2016), there are four general steps that must be conducted; de-contextualisation, re-contextualisation, categorisation, and compilation. After the data were collected from the interview, the researchers familiarised with the whole data, and separated them into smaller units (de-contextualising). After that, all the small units of data were examined as to whether they were appropriate and were needed to answer the objectives of the research. The inappropriate data were then expelled, while the information that corresponded with the research were secured (re-contextualising). Next, themes and codes were created. In order to scope the information, they were grouped based on the themes and codes identified (categorisation). Finally, the writing process started after the categories were already available (compilation). In this process, the researchers played an important role in extracting the essence of the data regarding the study. All of these coding processes were done by the help of a qualitative analysis software named *Dedoose* version 8.3.45. The 30 days free trial for student was used to obtain the full access of the software.

2.4.2 Quantitative Descriptive and Statistical Test

After the survey data were collected, they were converted into stacked bar charts for Likert-scale type questions to compare the modes from teachers' assessment on the three school safety pillars, and pie charts for the closed ended questions. The visuals help to illustrate the proportion and percentage of teachers responding to the questions on certain topics. Analysis was then given descriptively, although for some clarification, further statistical analysis such

as cross-tabulation and chi-squared were done to further examine the relationship between two different factors based on the responses given by teachers. By combining these analyses, it is expected that the quantitative data can present the teachers' perception on their assessment towards the current state of school safety during haze hazard, while the qualitative content analysis from interviewing experts could provide the reasoning and the causation of the quantitative results that have been generated.

2.5 Uniqueness and Limitations of the Study

The mixed methodology utilised in this research is useful to grasp more comprehensive views from both experts and practitioners on the ground. The data gained on the study, particularly the teachers' survey was relatively distinctive compared to the other majority of research examining school safety measures in Indonesia which usually take place in or relatively close to well-developed regions such as in the island of Java. Thus, in the case of haze hazard, the voices from respondents living in Sumatra and Kalimantan islands might give unique insights, particularly on behalf of school infrastructure development that are known to be not well-distributed in these regions.

Nevertheless, the amount of data samples involved in this study is still limited. The difficulty came across after a sudden shock due to the pandemic that coincided with the data collection time. This caused the onsite visit to the respective stakeholders, especially for the interview was cancelled. Despite of maximum efforts to invite interviewees online, technological barriers might also contribute for the potential candidate resided in the targeted areas. It is urged for the future study to obtain inputs from the local and regional stakeholders and practitioners that are lack of the presence in this occasion.

3. Results

3.1 Pillar One: Safe Learning Facilities

3.1.1 Experts' Narratives

Collapse of School Building in Past Disasters

The first element that the majority of the experts reflected upon in relation to past disaster events was about the collapse of school buildings. **G1, P1, P2 and P3** observe that from the disasters that occurred within the last three to four years, many schools' structures were easily broken down and degraded by various types of disaster. It has been found that school buildings in disaster prone areas often collapsed and resulted in significant infrastructure destruction afterwards. **P2** elaborates that based on the data of schools that were damaged during an earthquake such as the one in West Nusa Tenggara with magnitude of 6.2 that happened in 2020, around 250 schools were damaged. **P1** adds that ideally schools should be more persistent than other public facilities as many people often make them shelters in the aftermath of disasters. Fortunately, **P1** emphasises that so far, most fatal disasters have occurred in Indonesia outside of school days or hours so that the human casualties at schools tend to be minimum.

From what some of the experts have expressed above, it is explicit that the school infrastructure capability in Indonesia generally is far from ready in facing any disaster risks, including those from haze pollution. Some of the examples that are given concern obvious damage due to earthquakes, land-slides, or tsunamis, but this also indicates that they are even less-prepared to cope with other disaster risks such as haze. Though there are minimum human casualties from the collapse of school buildings in the past events, it is necessary to note that it happens due to the timing of disaster rather than resilient school infrastructures. **A2** has agreed with this point in which he highlighted on the discussions by stating that *“the collapse of so many school buildings during disasters might be an indication of how low disaster safety standards are for schools in Indonesia, and the lack of monitoring processes during their construction”*. That being said, the schools in haze impacted areas might have also experienced similar phenomenon, even worse if there are no standardised protocols that can minimise the haze risks. These issues, moreover, will be discussed in the following sub-sections in which the experts have clearly shown their concerns on this particular matter.

Lack of Disaster Safety Standards

The discussion on this topic begins with the observation from **G1** and **P2** that currently schools do not have certain specifications to construct the facilities according to local disaster risks. **P1** also envisages that generally, they are only built with a “normal” standard that school buildings should be built with in general no matter what kind of local disaster risks they have. He emphasises *“many kinds of infrastructure should be considered in school safety, including physical infrastructures of the buildings themselves, evacuation zones, first aid equipment, and supporting facilities”*. The general impression from those expert testimonies is that it seems the school building structures - particularly regarding the strength and design within Indonesia - are considered weak in terms of handling natural disasters. **G1** then reminds one of the plausible factors contributing to this which is in the past decades the Indonesian government constructed schools by implementing universal standards without deeply analysing the locality of the areas (such as contour, topography and natural landscape). This has led to a generic design not well suited to deal with many localised disaster risks.

Moreover, **G1** ensures that up to this date the building codes for constructing new schools are only prepared to cope with earthquakes – meaning there is no construction standards to cope with other disaster risks such as flood, tsunamis, land-slide, or haze. These are some of the factors that will likely counter any arguments that claim Indonesia’s school physical infrastructures are ready in coping with multi-hazard risks. **P1** also often found that both in terms of infrastructure standards and safety facilities, many schools do not have sufficient quality safety facilities – with emphasis given to the public schools – considering some private schools might have better quality facilities due to budget sufficiency.

Furthermore, based on the **P1**, **P3** and **A1** experiences on the field, they have witnessed that even issues as simple as door opening direction, window position, and furniture placement were often time wrongly designed to deal with localised disaster risks, thus causing troubles during evacuation time – though many of these small details started have gradually been taken care of over time. Another example given by **P1** is that many schools do not have evacuation signs and the schools in urban areas tend to have lack of space for meeting points during an evacuation.

According to **P2**, in many cases, though the school buildings are relatively new, they are not qualified to cope with local disasters. He clearly gives an example by saying that “*many school roofs are easily destroyed during typhoons because of no school building codes to face strong wind events*”. Interestingly, **G1** recognises that while some safety standards and guidelines are being provided at the national level in regards to earthquakes, most school buildings are generally not capable yet in facing other types of disasters that occur in their regions. However, **P3** argues some individual schools located in areas that frequently face a given hazard do have better building quality as a result of recovery processes from past experiences in facing big disaster events. **A1** supports this argument by indicating signs of better building quality among individual schools that have faced past disasters may appear in the form of the door size that has been made larger, or windows that are better positioned to ease the evacuation processes.

Meanwhile, some progressive development in school safety issues have been raised by the national government official. **G1** said that “*regarding the infrastructure readiness, there are no quantitative data that show the amounts of schools which have already met the safety standard against all disaster risks – the census concerning this building strength issues have not been done yet*”. However, **G1** informs that the technical guidelines for building new school infrastructures, such as for the construction of class rooms and other supporting facilities, have been launched. **G1** is also sure by further emphasising:

“Since 2011, the essence of school safety, practicality, and accessibility have been included in the national guidelines. Therefore, from 2011 onwards new school buildings should have implemented the newly provided safety standards for earthquake. Additionally, from 2018, the construction of schools was handed over to the Ministry of Public Work which are known to applying uniform quality standards in constructing facilities including to make them capable of coping with disaster risks such as earthquake”.

Based on **G1**'s elaboration above, the previously mentioned schools destroyed during past earthquakes might be the old buildings that were built before 2011 where the newly earthquake safety standards had not been launched. However, even if **G1**'s claim is true, it has no effect on the schools with the other type of disasters, particularly haze pollution.

Furthermore, in terms of other aspects such as the building layout design, the central government has included these into a national accreditation standard scheme. For example, **G1** mentions that schools accredited with an “A” or “B” rating must provide evacuation routes and zones, as well as early warning tools such as bells and the safety equipment. For the quantity of the equipment provision in particular, **P2** explains that the responsible agencies are currently developing the monitoring and evaluation systems that will assess all schools in Indonesia – around 523,000 schools in total. It is expected this evaluation system will fully identify the level of vulnerability of schools for what kind of damages the schools will likely have when disaster occurs; low, medium or heavy.

Despite of his optimistic views, **G1** also admits there are still huge amounts of schools that do not have or do not implement good safety standards – most of which were built before 2011. These might include the schools that were built during a massive school construction programme during the 1980s mandated by the president (INPRES) which did not prepare for disaster safety measures. In other words, the majority of Indonesia's school infrastructures do not meet the minimum safety standard against disasters in their current state – during the interview, **P1**, **P2**, **P3**, **A1** and **A2** seem to agree with this condition.

When it comes to a safety standard for haze pollution, **A1** realises that public society in general tend to have difficulty in assessing the risks for being exposed to haze. She adds that *“usually, people may just stay at home or find out a way to stay in a better ventilated building to avoid the polluted air, but little actual risk assessment seems to occur”*. **P1** also highlights that many people in the affected regions such as in Kalimantan or Sumatra that are haze prone have traditional wooden buildings which can be easily penetrated by the smoke – putting the children at high risk for haze exposure both at school and at home. According to **G1**, currently the central government has the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) to deal with haze events. **G1** envisages by stating: *“When the air quality index is above 200 or considered dangerous, the schools are strongly urged to close. Moreover, there is also another alternative available for installing safe classroom facilities, which is having the local governments provide the facilities while the national government will help in the design and planning processes. Additionally, since 2015, after the massive fires causing severe haze, the central government has developed various tools to purify the air quality in the class rooms so that they can be used safely for study”*.

Some of the tools mentioned above are for example the classroom’s air filtration and portable air purifier. However, regarding the applicability, it seems not common for the schools in haze affected regions to adopt. This has also been confirmed by **G1** in the discussion about obstacles in implementing school safety measures (refer to 3.2.1, *Challenges on Implementing Policies and Programmes*). In addition to this, the nationally initiated solutions are still found as difficult to be implemented in the local level – section 3.2.1 *The Vital Role of Local Entities* will also elaborate on this issue.

Weak Monitoring Systems

As with many other developing countries, the experts interviewed (**P1**, **P2**, **P3** and **A1**) seem to agree that one of the obstacles for safe school programmes in Indonesia is in the monitoring of the policy implementation. It is difficult to know whether the school infrastructures are capable of withstanding disasters, as monitoring processes that assess the building standards that should be applied and the test whether or not people are ready to face a given disaster are not well practiced.

A2 observed that there are plenty of cases where school management say that they have prepared for disaster risks, but when a disaster occurred, they do not do the responses as planned. Relating to this, **P2** thinks that the unpreparedness might be because of schools do not document properly the planning scenarios. Therefore, **P2** suggests the school management must have well-documented planning for disaster preparedness and these must be transparent for all school communities to access, including parents, security guards, staff, and students. **A2** further adds that weak monitoring systems also often give an opportunity for inappropriate acts, such as corruption on the purchase and application of construction materials which many different investigations have found.

The difficulty also varies among different types of hazards. **P1** mentions which in some cases, there are schools that must be relocated due to the risks that are too high – meaning any improved designs or reinforced building structures are still no match to the coming dangers. An example from the above statement is the schools that are located precisely on the shore

and too close to the sea – within the range of tsunami inundation. Unfortunately, **P1** and **A2** frequently witness similar cases when the school buildings have already been wiped out by massive waves of a tsunami, yet they are rebuilt in the same location. As for this phenomenon, **P2** refers to the destroyed schools being rebuilt in the exact same location in the region of Pangandaran, West Java in 2006 after a considerably large tsunami hit the area. From these discussions and the various examples given, it clearly shows that weak monitoring systems are among one of the serious challenges facing school safety in Indonesia.

3.1.2 Teachers' Perception on Pillar One

On behalf of teachers, the responses obtained are to learn about their opinions based on their experiences on the ground facing the haze pollution. There are six main questions representing indicators on their assessment related to the first pillar of school safety (safe learning facilities) within the haze pollution context. In total, 120 responses were gathered from the Likert-type questions. The six indicators extracted from the study framework in Pillar 1 include; school infrastructure capability, support from stakeholders, effectiveness of school building design, respiratory health equipment provision, school budget availability for green design, and air quality inside the classroom during haze events. The overall responses from these six indicators are then compiled to perform better visualisations for the analysis. The results can be seen on the following Figure 2.

Figure 2. Teachers' perception on safe learning facilities against haze

Based on the figure above, it is shown that three indicators received a 'very good' rating by ten percent or fewer of the respondents: school infrastructure capability, effectiveness of school building design, and respiratory health equipment provision. In terms of school infrastructure capability, only 10% teachers feel that it has been very good. Most respondents felt that their school's infrastructure capability was good (30.8%) or neither good nor bad (33.3%). Overall, most respondents felt good or indifferent about their school's infrastructure performances in coping with haze. However, 22.5% respondents stated their school's infrastructure was bad at coping with haze hazards, and 3.3% stated they were very bad very bad.

The building design of schools seems to be viewed as largely ineffective in coping with haze. Only a very small number of respondents (6.7%) stated their school's design was very good in coping with haze hazards. While nearly 36% of respondents say the effectiveness of building design is good, 27.5% teachers choose to be neutral, while an additional 24.2% say the design is bad for coping with haze hazards and 5.8% state the school design is very bad for coping with haze hazards. Similarly, views on health equipment provision during haze events was largely negative, with just 7.5% stating provisioning of health equipment was very good and 29.2% stating it was good. Nearly 26% teachers stated it was neither especially good nor bad, but this particular indicator has received the most bad (28.3%) and the second most very bad (9.2%) testimonies within all Pillar 1 indicators.

By contrast, the other three indicators, namely support from stakeholders, budget availability for green building design, and air quality inside the classrooms show quite good impressions from the respondents. The majority of teachers seem to agree that support from relevant stakeholders has been very good (28.3%) and good for the another 30.8%. Only an extremely small numbers of teachers (1.7%) say that the support is very bad and the another 15% say it is bad. In addition to this, the respondents believe that the schools have decent budget availability for initiating green design building. It is reflected by nearly 26% of respondents stating that budgeting for green design was very good and 27.5% stating it was good. This might be influenced by several factors as the school financial condition for issues like green design differs, particularly when it comes to provincial or local government support.

The last indicator which is about air quality in the classrooms during haze receives significant responses both for very good (25%) and very bad (16.7%) perceptions from teachers. Though 11.7% teachers report experiencing bad air quality, a number of respondents state that the air quality is good inside the classroom during haze events (34.2%). This sounds good indeed, however, it might be tricky to understand as this is subjective to teacher's perception. Some schools might have better ventilation and air filtration tools than the others. The air quality index during several haze events in the past over all of these regions often showed dangerous levels of toxic gases.

3.2 Pillar Two: School Disaster Management

3.2.1 Experts' Narratives

Improved Partnerships between Key Actors

Concerning this matter, most experts (**G1**, **P1**, **P2** and **P3**) tend to agree that the overall relationship between some of the key actors in school disaster management, such as the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) and the Ministry of Education and Culture are improving. Currently, the Indonesian government has what is a so-called *Satuan Pendidikan Aman Bencana* (SPAB) or Disaster Safety Education Unit that was initiated by multi-stakeholder partnerships which include the advocacy from NGOs and regional governments within the country. This national secretariat has very specific roles to support other key actors in escalating the progress on school safety related programmes.

There are many actors when it comes to school safety measures. **P3** states that in Indonesia, the major key actors in terms of policy are the Ministry of Education and Culture, Ministry of Religious Affairs, and the National Disaster Management Agency. **A2** also adds the regional and local budgeting agencies to include among the key actors since such programmes require proficient financial support. While in terms of knowledge, **P2** believes the school management itself holds many of the most significant roles. **A2** also argues that the crucial aspect is rather on how to strengthen the coordination between the key actors mentioned above, because effective policy implementation may not just involve one institution or organisation. The synergies on multi-stakeholder partnership are the key for successful school safety programmes in Indonesia according to the interviews.

The regulation about school safety has actually been provided – known as *Permendikbud No. 33 Tahun 2019* - where the roles of the Ministry of Education and Culture, local governments, and the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) have been regulated in order to initiate the *SPAB* pre-disaster, during a disaster, and in the aftermath of disasters. According to **G1**, the related documents concerning this new regulatory information have been distributed to schools though both in-person networking and online media. The national government also urges putting school safety as one of the indicators for national risks index that is annually issued by BNPB – so that school safety will be considered as one of the vital indicators that gives influence to overall regional scoring index reporting. **G1** reports in which up to this date, among the 73 variables on national risks index, two are specifically addressing school safety issues, though improvements on detailing the indicators are being considered for better future assessment. The improved multi-stakeholder partnerships and initiatives from the national government are good to hear – giving some light of hope among numerous struggles in Indonesia's school safety issues.

Challenges on Implementing Policies and Programmes

Based on the CSS framework, **A1** believes that the progress for Pillar 2 (school disaster management) in Indonesia has been more developed compared to Pillar 1 (safe learning facilities) and Pillar 3 (DRR and resilience education), both of which are relatively more challenging. Supporting the **A1** statement, **P2** has added that nowadays, though there are many activities that have been done by government bodies, NGOs and other parties to enhance school disaster preparedness in Pillar 2, the huge number of schools in Indonesia is one of the obstacles in policy implementation processes. **P2** also confirms that “in the last 10 years, for instance, there are roughly 400,000 education units that have been targeted and the current progress to

make them prepared is just reaching 100,000 schools”. In order to escalate this, the Ministry of Education and Culture has just launched a software named *Monev SPAB* to be used by schools so that authorities can monitor the progress in real time, according to **G1**. Unfortunately, no other clear plans to ensure whether schools are on the right track are currently in play. **P3** was also found through her field observations that many schools that begin to focus on disaster preparedness are the ones that have recently been struck by disasters such as those in Palu, Central Sulawesi, Lombok, and Yogyakarta. Eventually, this reactive type response could not guarantee that all other schools in disaster-prone areas are well-prepared.

Furthermore, extra willingness from school leaders such as headmasters is needed to better evaluate schools’ readiness. In many cases, **A2** has seen school management think that they are ready based on the self-assessment without considering further follow up actions for future improvement. In Aceh, however, **A1** clarifies as this phenomenon inspired universities to propose a regional law about school safety so that there is a stronger legal standing for allowing school management to allocate the budget for such programmes. This initiative was seen to be potential to be conducted because Aceh Province has been helped by many organisations after the Indian Ocean Tsunami, and the efforts from these organizations means that the government has the experience dealing with this particular issue.

Moreover, **A1** has observed that most of the programmes about school safety were utilising a top-down approach, an approach the government keeps using with many different school-based activities; healthy school, anti-corruption school, Adiwiyata clean school, and many others. This type of approach has caused school management to be overwhelmed in managing its work load. Therefore, it is believed that more bottom-up initiatives in regulating school safety are needed. The initiative to propose local regulation in conducting school activity, such as the one in Aceh as **A1** has mentioned earlier, is expected to give alternative options for schools whether or not they allocate the budget and conduct the school safety programmes depending on their need and school’s risk priority.

A2 also suggests during the interviews that key actors on DRR in Indonesia, such as the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) and the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD), should expand their collaboration with schools and education institutions. There has been lack of coordination in terms of policy implementation in the field of disaster management within schools. For example, **A2** often witnesses situations in which among many initiatives launched by central government such as School Readiness Towards Disasters or *Sekolah Siaga Bencana* (SSB) are often found to be stuck in the socialisation phase. Seemingly, lack of pro-active movements is among one of the determining factors in this matter. Additionally, authorities must collaborate with Higher Education Institutions to reach out the rest of society. As **A2** has pointed out, in higher education campus environments, there are social service programmes or *Kuliah Kerja Nyata* (KKN) that have the mandate to send the students to the villages prior to their graduation. This is indeed a perfect opportunity for BNPB and BPBD to train students so then they can support local inhabitants in disaster prone areas.

However, when it comes to haze hazard, there is a sense of irony when **G1** mentions a collaboration plan between the SPAB secretariat and Bandung Institute of Technology (ITB) in the implementation of air purification tool projects was cancelled just because the coming rainy season is approaching – again, reflecting a short-term reactive behaviour from the relevant key actors. **P1** highlights another driving factor that may lead to the lack of

coordination concerning the management of schools is that schools within Indonesia are under different ministries, such as Islamic schools that are distinctively authorised by the Ministry of Religious Affairs instead of the Ministry of Education and Culture. While many private Islamic schools have their independent disaster management programmes regarding school safety and disaster response, there is not necessarily coordination working between the two systems in regards to disaster management.

Budget limitations, moreover, have contributed to the obstacles facing comprehensive disaster management within Indonesia's schools. **A2** was concerned regarding the many different cases when there is no budget allocated for school safety in regional government, and therefore school management can do very little. Although, **A1** argues that improving the safety of school facilities actually can be done from small and simple things such as changing the door direction or setting better table positions, many safety measures require substantial budgeting. Relying on the central government for this budgeting does not seem to be a prominent solution either. According to **G1**, the national government has indeed allocated some funding, however, it would not be enough to cover all school across the country. He adds that *"in 2015 alone, for instance, there were 49,000 schools affected by haze in several provinces; Jambi, Riau, Palembang (South Sumatra), West Sumatra, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan and others"*. Consequently, supplying all of those regions continues to be a serious challenge.

To better understand the lack of budgetary resources which can affect school mitigation efforts on haze pollution cases, **G1**'s expresses this approximation based on the experience in handling issues. He illustrates:

"In the case of haze, the cost for installing air purification tools is about 1 to 1.5 million rupiah (around 80-100 USD) per class room. If there are around 50,000 schools that the central government must support, it is obviously extremely costly to make all classes well-prepared in dealing with haze pollution in this manner".

Instead, the SPAB national secretariat has the guidance for learning processes during emergency situation including severe haze events which seems to be more applicable. **A2** suggests the other alternative in terms of funding is to look at the School Operational Aid or *Bantuan Operasional Sekolah* (BOS). **P2**, **P3**, **A1** and **A2** however, criticise the guidelines and details that require schools to refer to specific programme proposals which are not clear to follow. On top of this, budgeting issues are commonly known to be a serious problem within the country's bureaucracy.

The Vital Role of Local Entities

As some of the experts interviewed have been mentioned on the previous discussions regarding the local stakeholders, their roles in disaster management for schools are considered significant. **P1**, **P2**, **P3**, **A1** and **A2** reiterate that "the most challenging aspect in relation to school safety is to ensure the implementation of established policy particularly by local governments and school management". Though the guidelines and standards are provided by the national government, the practises rely heavily on the local government and school management. For example, **P2** believes that priority budgeting for disaster reduction related

efforts should be decided by school themselves – as the needs vary amongst different schools. Though there are some policy initiatives from the ministries and national disaster agencies, according to **A2** based on various implementation projects, the disaster management activities at the individual school level still needs to be boosted by national government. **G1** then confirms this is also one of the drivers for establishing the Disaster Safety Education Unit (SPAB) secretariat in 2019 by the Ministry of Education and Culture.

Another common difficulty revealed by interviews with the experts is that neither headmasters nor local governments have a complete understanding or clear priority action plans for the disaster related programmes in order to make their given regions being well-prepared. As **P1** has stated “the comprehensive existing guidelines provided by IGOs such as UNESCO or other entities regarding school safety are not often adopted by local authorities”. The nationally-initiated programmes such as the SPAB need the support of regional and local political leaders that are highly influential in sustaining them at the school level. This has been confirmed by **P2** in which he says:

“once the regional leaders decide them nationally-initiated programmes on disaster management in schools are a priority, it is believed that all other parties - namely the regional education agencies, headmasters, and teachers - will take part”.

P3 strengthens the statement by highlighting that many local governments took initiatives during haze events in 2019 by issuing an official letter to instruct schools to be closed due to severe haze risks. This kind of local initiative is seen to be effective at critical times so that school children will not be put in high-risk condition while waiting for national government action. Thus, it seems that more locally-initiated innovations and actions are better in tackling the disaster risks for hazards such as haze.

Furthermore, the discussion with **A2** revealed that there are complicated local context politics that influence the school management leadership. **A1** also agrees on this point in which she believes the school communities are known to work very well when the headmaster is transparent in managing the budget from the government. However, **A2** emphasises there are some cases where headmasters themselves are proven to be corrupt. **A2** also speculates:

“in many regions of the country, the elected political leaders - such as a provincial governor or regent - are often involved in influencing the appointment of regional stakeholder chiefs including the regional education bureau and school headmasters. These tend to be people who express support to the newly elected leaders and their political parties – even though these persons may be without relevant capabilities”.

Consequently, **P2** recommends that the limited resources which are available should not only be used for training the large amounts of teachers, but also for training headmasters who may lack relevant school management experience for implementing DRRE or school safety programmes. **P1**, **P3**, **A1** and **A2** have also similarly recommended putting more efforts into persuading the local leaders to commit to ensuring all education units are prepared to face hazardous events that are found in their region. Moreover, based on the crosstab and chi-square statistical test, the way teachers contribute to DRR efforts at school does not correlate with the trainings that they have already received. More detail on this test result can be seen on sub-chapter 4.3.3.

A unique experience in Aceh was also shared by **A1**. This experience began with her curiosity on why various school safety programmes such as School Safety Education Unit

(SPAB), School Safety Against Disaster (SAB), Islamic School Safety Against Disaster (MAB) and others were not practised continuously in many schools in the region. After having discussions with many headmasters from various schools around Aceh region, **A1** recognised some patterns of responses when teachers were asked to explain the reasons. She then envisages:

“the headmasters often thought that school safety programmes require much money and they are reluctant to allocate this in school budgeting plans – worrying about the risks for being accused of corruption for what community members may seem as arbitrary expenses”.

However, there was one distinct school leader who shared a successful experience in allocating a budget for school safety activities and also integrated the programmes in the school’s “Vision & Mission” to provide transparency. As a result of this clever move, the headmaster never worried from any inappropriate allegations and the school safety initiatives had successfully been conducted in the school. **A1** expressed that this leader was an inspiration and should have motivated the other fellow headmasters to follow a similar course of actions. It clearly shown that the willingness of school leaders in taking initiative to sustain the school safety programmes at the school level. Moreover, the headmasters should not be over-concerned for being accused of corruption as long as they can provide transparency for school safety resources to the public and authorities.

Interviews revealed that leadership personalities within schools matter, as these will often determine whether or not the school innovations and activities related to DRRE can survive on their own or must continually rely on support from external organisations or the national government. **P3** has been seen in many cases where teachers are eager to contribute to the school safety programmes but they do not have support from the leadership – and thus often fail to sustain the efforts. In addition to this, the school communities should also have the capability to manage risks. **P2** expresses that it is critical for school communities to know what the risks are in their school, how to be better prepared, and how to deal with them. **P2** also emphasises:

“DRR issues should be included in the school yearly plan, including within budget allocation. The headmasters must understand the action plan in order to lead the other school components in implementing school safety programmes”.

Meanwhile, most of the interviewees strongly recommend for school management to seek help from the regional disaster mitigation agency (BPBD), NGOs, or experts that can guide them in documenting their school’s risk management plan adequately – in case the headmasters are not capable. This might be relevant to the case of haze pollution where it has been less commonly addressed by the school management compared to other well-known hazards, such as earthquakes, flooding, and volcanic eruptions. Last but not least, linking the risk data for the school with the regional database on disaster risk that already exist in municipalities or cities might strengthen the school against disaster risks – all must be integrated.

3.2.2 Teachers' Perception on Pillar Two

In terms of teacher's point of view on the Pillar 2: School Disaster Management, it seems that the responses represent that better progress has been made compared to the previous pillar (Figure 2). Generally, the responses indicate overall good, or neither good nor bad experiences, significantly more than bad experiences. Some indicators that receive good responses are regarding school community response and collaboration with stakeholders.

First and foremost, the teachers stated that they experience very good (9.2%) and good (37.5%) school community response during haze events. This has come from almost a half of the total respondents. The other nearly half (40%) of the rest of respondents could not decide by stating that the response is neither good nor bad. However, only a small amount of teachers (0.8%) think that that school community had very bad and bad (12.5%) responses against haze pollution. Looking at the other indicators, moreover, it can be seen that teachers express that their schools have good collaboration with stakeholders (41.7%), disaster mitigation planning (36.7%) and follow appropriate guidelines (39.2%) – all the numbers are within the range of around 40% or nearly half of the total responses. One thing that shows quite a significant drop in good response (28.3%) is regarding the school management preparedness. This particular indicator also receives the most significant numbers of bad (19.2%) and very bad (3.2%) responses related to Pillar 2 which have around 15% of teachers reporting the bad category and usually less than 2.5% of teachers for the very bad category.

Figure 3. Teachers' perception on school disaster management against haze

The distinct pattern that indicates teacher's lack of positive sentiments towards the school management preparedness during haze pollution is a cause for concern. This might be related to what has been revealed by the previous discussions with the experts in which some school

leaders are not aware of school safety issues though they are considered as the most influential local actors. Moreover, a number of teachers expressed neither bad nor good impressions of school management preparedness (38.3%) as well as to the school community response (40%). This neutral option is indeed tricky to interpret, however, choosing a relatively safe answer it may just represent the lack of knowledge from the respondents on behalf of the particular issues, or they might feel as there are not many changes from the status quo between pre-, during, and the aftermath of disasters – in other words business as usual – to represent their views. However, the high level of ambivalence on both of these questions is likely not just a coincidence since the management capability in responding to disasters may influence the community response as well.

This has been once again a reminder for highlighting the crucial role of school leaderships for the improvement of school disaster management. The overall quality of school leaders in the haze affected regions can also be assessed from the pattern on this survey result. Another analysis that comes up is regarding good stakeholder relationships, as previously discussed in the interview results. The survey results also show that the collaboration of schools with stakeholders is the most progressive among all indicators in this pillar.

Overall, several indicators within Pillar 2 regarding school disaster management have received considerably good responses from teachers compared to the previous Pillar 1 about safe learning facilities. This result seems to synchronise with the interview results as Pillar 2 was shown to have some progress particularly in terms of stakeholder partnerships from the interviews. However, the room for improvement is still wide open, particularly regarding weak school management preparedness, which was strongly related to school leadership capacity. The interview result also shows that school management needs to be supported in better understanding the importance of school safety initiatives and programmes within Indonesian school settings.

3.2.3 Examining the Correlation Between Teachers' Training and Attitude in DRR Efforts

Responding to the discussion on the previous section (3.2.1) in which some experts recommend to train policy makers and local leaders instead of heavily targeting teachers for DRRE training, this particular sub-chapter will examine whether the given trainings have a significant influence towards teachers' contribution in reducing haze risks at their schools. First of all, the following Figure 4 will describe the proportion of teachers that receive training and/or capacity building in relation to DRR. From the chart it can be seen that out of 120 respondents, more than half (51.3%) have received such trainings, while the other 48.7% state that they never experienced any. Though there are more respondents that have obtained such trainings, the proportion between the two groups still relatively even. Among the training and capacity building that teachers receive, DRR education related activities dominate with 25.2% followed by disaster drill with 14.3%. The rest of the respondents say that they receive trainings in relation to school disaster mitigation (4.2%), education for sustainable development (4.2%) and others (3.4%).

Figure 4. Training and capacity building received by teachers

Apart from the numbers of teachers and the training types they receive, it is interesting to see whether or not these kinds of training have significantly driven teachers' contribution to DRR efforts in their school. There are several different contributions or efforts that the respondents' claims were done in their respective schools. The detail from survey result can be seen on the following Figure 5.

Figure 5. Teachers' efforts to reduce haze pollution risks at school

It can be seen on Figure 5 above that more than a half (53%) teachers contribute to reduce haze risks in school by raising awareness to wear mask. The other majority of respondents (30.8%) contribute by teaching students about haze pollution. These two groups alone have comprised of more than 80% of the respondents. The other minority responses are the efforts regarding participation in disaster mitigation planning (7.7%), communication to parents about haze impacts (6.8%), and even some who do not contribute at all (1.7%). Considering the dominant result on the two efforts (awareness raising to wear masks and teaching students about haze pollution), it gets more compelling to check if these certain attitudes are actually

driven by the trainings that half of teachers have received. Therefore, cross tabulation and chi-squared (X^2) statistical test are utilised to examine the correlation between them.

On the Table 2 it can be seen that the proportion between trained and untrained teachers on the type of efforts looks very similar in numbers – meaning there is no significant differences. For example, out of 61 teachers who contribute by raising awareness to wear a mask, 33 of them said to have received the training and 28 of them are not. It is pretty similar on the other type of contributions; teaching students about haze (19 untrained and 18 trained), communicate with parents (3 untrained and 5 trained), contribute in school disaster mitigation (5 untrained and 4 trained).

Though it might look quite obvious, a chi-square test is conducted to make sure the level of significance. A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between DRR related training and contribution to DRR related efforts at school by teachers. The result comes out by confirming that the relation between these variables was not significant, $X^2(1, N = 115) = 0.8322, p = .841761$. From this result, it can be seen that the relation between training and teachers' contribution towards DRR efforts in their school is *not* significant at $p < .05$. The total respondents being tested is 115 out of 120 because 5 teachers correspond to the ones that state they do not contribute at all which then to be excluded, because the test will only examine the teachers that contribute to DRR efforts at their school.

Table 2. The correlation between training to teachers and their contribution on DRR efforts at school

Results						
	Awareness raising for wearing masks	Teaching students about haze	Remind parents about haze risks	Actively contributed in school disaster planning and mitigation		Row Totals
Never received DRR related training	28 (29.17) [0.05]	19 (17.70) [0.10]	3 (3.83) [0.18]	5 (4.30) [0.11]		55
Received DRR related training	33 (31.83) [0.04]	18 (19.30) [0.09]	5 (4.17) [0.16]	4 (4.70) [0.10]		60
Column Totals	61	37	8	9		115 (Grand Total)

The result from this correlation test attached to the previous suggestions from the experts' interviews where it is suggested to not utilise the limited government budget to only focus on teachers' training but should also seriously target the other local stakeholders and leadership roles, in addition to the established capacity building for relevant educational organisations and institutes. It is known that teachers have already been burdened by numerous responsibilities outside of their main task for teaching the students. Thus, teachers' training on DRR related efforts are better to integrate within the already existing programmes for professional teachers' development. It would be considered as unwise to spend the limited budget to overwhelm the teachers in which the programme may not be efficient to influence teachers' efforts in DRR.

3.3 Pillar Three: Risk Reduction and Resilience Education

3.3.1 Experts' Narratives

Flexibility of Indonesia's National Curriculum

Regarding the curriculum, interviews revealed that geography and social studies are considered the most related subjects to incorporate DRR into teaching. **A2** assumes that in the Indonesian national curriculum, the DRR related topics are lacking—presumably just 5-10% within all subjects in the secondary school. However, **A2** also believes that a lack of representation of DRR related topics in the curriculum has not been a serious problem since teachers are allowed to do adjustments and use innovations in delivering the topics to the classes. This was widely regarded in the interviews as a chance to eliminate the barriers in incorporating DRR related issues based on the locality of the risks in many different regions in the country.

A2 further emphasises that the integration can be done in many ways, such as an adjustment in the subject contents and even the utilisation of learning media in the topics or subjects that would not otherwise teach students about disasters. For example, as **P2** mentions “*when students learn the Indonesian language, they can read news on the internet concerning newly occurring hazards which can be reviewed in language class. And, while teaching students physical education, teachers could innovate by setting up a tsunami-like condition and conduct an evacuation drill together with the students*”. In geography, moreover, students can study map of disaster risks in their neighbourhood or other nearby selected locations. There are many opportunities in existing curricula for not only understanding the existing curricular content, but for supplementing this disaster education.

Based on **P3's** extensive experiences on the field, it has been shown that integrating DRR topics with extracurricular activities can be effective in enhancing the student's life skills, providing a useful combination to cognitive skills for coping with disasters. Decent implementation of these initiatives may be done when teachers are also able to evaluate and adjust their workload in order to create the balance and avoid being overwhelmed. The most recent example that proves the national curriculum's flexibility is the current adaptive version for facing the COVID-19 pandemic by the establishment of distance study for all school levels.

However, some experts interviewed (**P3, A1, and A2**) argue that the national curriculum has still not been able to incorporate DRR education systematically – any examples that have been mentioned previously are considered partial integration or improvisation. They suggested in the interviews that a good way to begin improving the curriculum understanding towards DRR is by mapping the basic competencies for DRR in education.

Knowledge Barriers Among School Community

Both interviews and the survey data indicate that preparedness of school community for disasters is considered as good in general, however, institutional readiness seems to be less prepared. This might be due to lack of ground level policy implementation and initiatives. Some misconceptions are also often found in the field. **A1** has given an instance: “*regarding tsunamis, there are a lot of simulations that teach people to check whether the sea level drops as an indication of the coming huge waves. However, this is an inaccurate understanding, and unfortunately, has been commonly taught nationally*”. Moreover, the knowledge and skills that school community obtains are often limited and lack of details. **A2** mentions that “*some of the students or teachers might know about hiding under the table when earthquake happens,*

but what kind of table should they choose? Are there enough strong or standardised tables to hide in the classrooms?” A2 believes these assumptions are questionable.

Universities play an important position in distributing valid information and knowledge in relevant efforts related to DRR education. Teachers have a strategic contribution in fostering better teaching to students on DRR related topics. According to **P2**, based on the latest evaluation report on Indonesia’s school safety, the quality of the students’ understanding disaster is strongly influenced by their teachers. Teachers also have an ideal position in communicating with parents to increase awareness outside the school environments. **P2** urges for advocating the leadership, such as the headmaster, to encourage DRR curriculum which is also a prominent option for teachers to strengthen institutional capability at the school level.

Meanwhile, training and capacity building ideally must be conducted comprehensively. According to **G1**, conducting a face-to-face training event on this topic nationally has been found challenging – stating, *“how many class rooms are required?”* He further illustrated that for instance, *“the SPAB initiative will take around 3 to 4 days to conduct and the maximum capacity for such a training is usually 150 teachers. If the number of active teachers need to receive the trainings are around 4 million people, it will require a lot of facilitators and activities to be conducted”*.

To cope with this issue, the government often shares the knowledge through online platforms. The online technical guidance has been practised quite frequently with quizzes and exams, and **G1** claims there are approximately 10,000 teachers that have already participated in the online capacity building as of 2020. In the SPAB initiative, the training consists of 8 modules for teachers to study and follow the processes until they finally qualify to take the exams. Certificates are given when participants acquire the minimum score of 80. This initiative from the national SPAB secretariat is voluntary and will not likely be made compulsory because teachers also handle numerous other teaching-related responsibilities and initiatives, such as anti-corruption school, Adiwiyata school, healthy schools, and others.

Furthermore, school location means different learning opportunities. **P1** argues that in big cities, school students often have a visitation to a disaster mitigation agency office and other relevant institutes. However, schools situated in rural areas have limited access to such privileges. The National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) and its subordinate are also considered new organs launched around 13 years ago in 2008 – thus **P1** also believes many personnel in smaller regions have limited specific capability to train general public or schools in particular. Meanwhile, **P3** gives an alternative option that she has conducted frequently in the past, urging activities to support school safety initiatives for students to be practised more with intervening in extracurricular programmes such as scouts and red cross.

For the teachers, moreover, **P2** believes that it is vital to train them for enabling disaster management planning at schools, and also to create lesson plans that integrate DRR related matters into the curriculum. However, **P3** reminds that the role of teachers can change depending on the context, as teachers themselves can become victims during disasters. But in general, **P3** also agrees in which teachers must be ready to lead students anytime during disaster occurrences and they should be able to conduct psycho-social support for the vulnerable children as well. During an evacuation drill, teachers should be trained to not panic in order to escort the students calmly to safe locations. Thus, the valuable psychosocial skills and basic understanding of early warning systems have to be included in the drilling practices.

Furthermore, programmes to enhance teacher's capacity in a systematic way is required. So far, **A2** has seen the existing capacity building programmes are limited and sporadic. Vast amounts of teachers do not have opportunity to participate in disaster education facilitator training. Incorporating capacity building programmes into the existing and regular agenda that teachers have been mandated to take during their professional career is strongly suggested by **A1**. Regarding students, they generally seem to have good disaster education knowledge. However, **A1** views it as necessary to ensure that the knowledge and training that the students perceived could be transformed into daily habits so that they will always be conscious – more than just acquiring theoretical or cognitive skills, it should become their wisdom.

These knowledge barriers mentioned by the interviewees might have also existed in the case of haze pollution. Though the flexibility of national curriculum provides a way to incorporate topics related to haze, the practical knowledge which leads to surviving skills during haze events must be considered further. Making students be aware of the risk of being exposed to toxic gases will definitely help them in reducing the short and long-term risks such as the decreased life expectancy. More than that, better awareness among all school communities will also enable the learning practices with less disturbance, thus will keep ensuring good quality education for all children.

3.3.2 Teachers' Perception on Pillar Three

At a glance, teachers' responses toward Pillar 3: risk reduction and resilience education indicate the most positive result, even more than the previous Pillar 2. This might be supported by the high adaptability of the national curriculum for DRRE teaching as it has been discussed on the previous sub-sections on the expert interview results. Some indicators that are used in this last pillar include; students understanding of haze hazards, curriculum contents for teaching DRRE, level of confidence in teaching DRRE, teaching of haze-related impacts to students, and DRRE in school curriculum. Overall, the positive trends can be easily identified by looking at Figure 6.

Among the majority of positive responses, a bad testimony is given in relation to the DRRE in school curriculum. Though this indicator sounds slightly similar to the other (curriculum contents for teaching DRRE), it has sharp differences. The DRRE in school curriculum questions teachers' perspectives as to how the DRRE has been incorporated comprehensively and as a whole concept to make DRRE more holistic in school learning processes. This has to do not only about DRRE curricular content, but also the other aspects of learning such as the learning media preferences, routine evacuation drills, and extracurricular activities. The result on this particular indicator had the mostly bad responses (13.3%) among the other indicators in Pillar 3. This supports the claims made in the interviews, that the school curriculum has not been always been able to systematically incorporate DRRE despite its high flexibility to ability to adjust to localized contexts. The indicator shows bad (6.7%) and very bad (2.5%) responses regarding students understanding on haze hazards. This indicator has a close tie to the previous one that has been discussed, since curriculum directly impacts on students' learning activities. However, these numbers are still a more general perception among teachers within the current

time frame. Thus, this can be more validated by conducting an assessment study that specifically addresses student’s cognitive understanding on haze hazards in the future.

Figure 6. Teachers’ perception on Risk Reduction and Resilience Education

On the other hand, other categories received generally positive feedback from the respondents. It can be seen that teaching about haze impacts to students is largely perceived by teachers as very good (29.2%) and good (35%). Similarly, the curriculum contents for teaching DRRE are represented by the highest good response among all the other indicators within Pillar 3 (55%), with an additional 13.3% stating it was very good. These positive trends coincide with the interview results, in which it is revealed that the national curriculum has an incredibly adaptive form in terms of its contents to be adjusted for localized DRRE teaching objectives.

Moreover, the most positive trend is seen among the indicator for level of confidence in teaching DRRE with nearly 27% teachers saying they were having a very good confidence and more than half claimed to have good confidence. This is an interesting perception considering there is still lack of teachers training and capacity building according to the expert interviews. However, as has been pointed out by the experts in the previous discussions, this seems to confirm the high level of awareness among school communities on disasters. including teachers. The problem is, this relatively high awareness is not equipped with high preparedness. This also might be the reason why one of the experts stated that there is a lack of details among school community’s knowledge concerning disasters – and training and capacity building might still be required to improve these drawbacks.

4. Discussion

4.1 Issues addressed by the study: Intersection of ESD, School safety and DRR Education

This study is categorised as the one that is related to a very broad field known as Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) with a specification in DRR education focusing on school safety. Due to its broad focus, UNESCO (2005) define the characteristics of ESD include but are not limited to; principles and values of sustainable development, promoting life-long learning, addressing content by taking into account context, global issues and local priorities, and engaging with formal, non-formal and informal education. This means educational studies with a focus related to wide array of issues within sustainable development can be identified as part of ESD. Examples of this include many of the so-called adjectival education fields, such as human rights education, environmental education, climate change education, and includes DRR education in which this study is situated.

Shibao (2014) adds that ESD is interpreted as a broad study which may include all themes and perspectives from other related education, therefore, though adjectival education core values may vary, but remain interconnected with ESD in general. A definition of DRR education has been shown by the study from Santa-Cruz et al., (2016) where institutional arrangements, collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches – which have been identified as community-based elements – are used to develop a multi-scale risk model to reduce risks at schools in Lima, Peru. Magni et al. (2017) frame DRR education thru policy studies, examining emergency preparedness and response capability in an Italian university which also involves the use of a survey tool to investigate the role of student body and organisations during emergency events.

Historically, there were several initiatives before and after the formal establishment of Comprehensive School Safety (CSS) by the Global Alliance for Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience in the Education Sector (GADRRRES) in 2012 rooted from South East Asian Country initiatives. It is believed that various man-made and natural disasters had impacted school aged children and youth severely – not only physically but also mentally – both in a short-and-long term period of time (Paci-Green et al., 2019). Among the psychosocial impacts that affect children are sleeping disorders, anxiety, depression and behavioural illness.

In the early 2000s, several initiatives were rising to urge the necessity in addressing the issues of school safety and risk reduction in the education sector. UN bodies such as UNICEF started with launching several programmes, among them the School Safety Initiative as well as Child Friendly Schools, for ensuring quality of education in the middle of armed conflict in Nigeria (Wright et al., 2009). At the same time, the minimum standards for children and adults in emergency condition was developed by the Interagency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE) in order to ensure safe learning continuation (Paci-Green et al., 2019).

In 2014, the Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack (GCPEA) was initiated to enhance monitoring and reporting processes of attacks on school or educational infrastructures around the planet. The coalition released an independent report called Education Under Attack in 2018. As a non-profit organisation, the members also include co-chairs from Human Rights Watch and Save the Children, the Council for At-Risk Academics (CARA), the Institute of International Education (IIE), the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for

Refugees (UNHCR), the Education Above All Foundation (EAA), the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (EUA, 2018). In addition to this, the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) together with the Global Alliance for Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience in the Education Sector (GADRRRES) launched the Worldwide Initiative for Safe Schools (WISS) aimed at providing safety for new schools from disasters (UNDRR, 2014). In 2017, in order to assure better implementation and to bring about the update, the CSS was endorsed with its more child-centred and evidence-based efforts in reducing disaster risks in the education sector (UNDRR, 2017).

4.2 The Importance of DRRE for Indonesian Schools

Global climate change has increased the number of disaster risks on the planet. According to UNDRR Global Assessment Report (GAR, 2020) the increase of hazard exposure both in higher and lower income nations has increased way faster than vulnerability has decreased – this also means that the amount of new risks being faced are exceeding the already existing risks being reduced. This includes the increased risks from disaster in public facilities like schools. Numerous disasters have impacted countless school children and communities; earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, and floods, not to mention haze pollution. The types of disaster being faced depends on the geographical locations of the school. For example, in Nepal, the majority of schools are at extreme risk from earthquake (Tuladhar, 2013). While in Indonesia, as an archipelagic country with significant numbers of active volcanos, many types of disaster occur and these risks may be greater in the coming future with a changing climate and growing population.

Natural disasters may occur unpredictably over time, and one of the challenges concerned by the expert during interviews is knowing that most school aged individuals spend most of their day time every week at schools. This means that the capability of personnel at the schools in responding to hazards is a vital aspect of disaster response. Furthermore, schools are not only learning systems, but are also systems of infrastructure. The buildings, for instance, are usually constructed in a uniform way across different areas and have many classrooms, spacious assembly spots, long hallways, and other usages of space and infrastructure that contribute to the challenges in responding to disasters. Ironically, though school infrastructures are known to be vulnerable when they are located in hazardous areas, often time they are used as shelters or community centres both during and after the occurrence of disasters (Kelman, 2011 & Petal et al., 2015). D'Ayala et al. (2020) suggest that assessing multi-hazard vulnerability and risk of school buildings have been considered as one of the urgent tasks for stakeholders and responsible authorities. Most importantly, it is also vital for governments to set more strategic views in the face of the coming extreme type events by considering infrastructure designs and operations as well as cascading impacts in relation to disaster (Pearson et al., 2018). This cannot be more concerning by knowing that the interview has revealed in which the only disaster safety standard ready to utilise for constructing new schools in Indonesia is for earthquake – leaving the other disaster risks untouched.

The importance of school safety seems to be late in coming to Indonesia compared to the awareness on other issues within disaster risk reduction contexts. An interesting study by Suppasari et al., (2015) about ten years aftermath of the Indian ocean tsunami in Indonesia that examines the reconstruction, emergency response, and disaster awareness related matters such as DRR education reveals that amongst the major components that were assessed, self-reliance, community, and the local industries had been categorised as well recovered – indicated by routine evacuation drill and fully operational hotels and public facilities within the 10 years period after the tsunami. However, disaster risk reduction education and culture have shown little improvement, existing, but with various limitations in practice (Suppasari, et al., 2015).

In addition, Wegscheider (2011) studies the risk assessment methodology to identify the potential loss of life in high tsunami risk areas in Indonesia. It is stated that the high and very high-risk areas do not have enough capacity and capability in facing a tsunami. For example, there are often a lack of prominent shelters in the area with high hazard intensity, which will increase the chance of buildings people do take shelter in collapsing. Furthermore, related to community education – it is suggested that authorities must have better disaster management including in disseminating early warnings, enabling community members to understand the disaster risk, and to properly respond in case of emergency. Prioritising specific zones might help authorities to accelerate their actions if there are a lack of resources to cover wide areas (Wegscheider, 2011). Meanwhile, a study conducted by Hermon et al., (2019) concerning the assessment of Sinabung volcano risks in North Sumatra suggests that the Karo Regency government must include relocation, disaster education, enhanced socialisation in disaster prone zones, and disaster-based spatial planning in all disaster responses going forward. For disaster education particularly, it is strongly urged that the responsible stakeholders must initiate disaster education curricula at all levels of school (elementary to secondary) to better build a culture of safety and resilience among local communities.

Eventually, these studies among the other various research recommend that the disaster risk reduction education is required to be strengthened further. The slow progress in education in disaster risk reduction is attached to the fact that in the global level, the integration of disaster risk reduction and disaster response into education sector policy was less prevalent, making school communities in developing countries become all the more vulnerable (Amri et al., 2017; Sheffield et al., 2017). The policy implementation on the ground shows up as the major challenge that may hamper such initiatives in integrating the two sectors. One of the reasons for this is because working with the local governments and authorities on integrating policy agendas takes a considerably long-time, but their support is considered vital for helping to shape general public's awareness towards disasters (Fathani, et al., 2016). This vital role of local actors and leaderships has also been discussed by the experts on the interview section, particularly in regards of Pillar 2 of school safety. Apart from the above-mentioned obstacles, there is another future challenge to be faced in the form of climate change that has started to make some disasters occur more frequently, or to become more dangerous and uncertain. Therefore, in facing the disaster risks exacerbated by climate change in educational settings, the efforts must go beyond what is known as business as usual (Rahayu et al., 2020).

4.3 Regional Cooperation and Localisation of Action

The research by Isa & Sugiyanto (2018) and Susilowati (2018) have pointed out that exposure can be the most influencing factor to the vulnerability level of population in disaster prone areas. This is strongly related to the case of haze pollution hazards, where millions of people including students are put in an extremely high level of exposure to toxic substances that threatens their respiratory health systems. Moreover, in managing the risks, vulnerability levels cannot be underestimated. Putting vulnerability problems as a sectional part of disaster risk reduction could produce narrow solutions which are not effective for the community to acknowledge (Rahman, M.B., and Harahap, T., 2019). Finding an effective way to work with community is indeed a vital aspect in addressing disaster risk reduction. Lassa et al., (2018) conducted a study about Community Based Disaster Risk Reduction (CBDRR) in eastern Indonesia which reveal a clear example where CBDRR that aimed to recognise the roles of local community and capacity has made the locals have better practices in dealing with floods and droughts over the last 20 years. The authors also argue that the planning in Tonieke should be extended beyond agriculture to include education, shelter, and nutrition, as well as social policies within the region. It is also noted that social changes need a long time to succeed, something that is difficult for NGOs and donors to accomplish in a short amount of time.

Consequently, appropriate strategies in tackling the issues must be carefully considered to ensure better results in the implementation of disaster risk reduction efforts. Not to mention, there are more complex disasters occurring recently, including risks of transboundary disasters such as haze pollution, in addition to cascading as well as compound disasters as a result of climate change. Shi et al., (2016) suggests that one way to better understand these is by strengthening regional exchange on disaster risk information. For the haze pollution hazard which has been the focus of this particular thesis study, the South East Asian Countries must continue their collaboration efforts in disaster risk reduction in order to fully integrate disaster risk reduction into their societies, including into school safety procedures. One of the regional frameworks concerning disaster management that has been ratified by the Association of South East Asian Nations members is the ASEAN Agreement on Disaster Management and Emergency Response (AADMER) – launched in 2005 and entered into force by late 2009.

Besides regional cooperation, localisation has also been an important aspect to develop, particularly if it is related to health risk management such as for mitigating the haze pollution impacts. According to Tatsuhiko (2019), there are five key research areas that need to be emphasised regarding Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management (Health-EDRM) such as haze pollution. The review reveals that local facilities tend to be overwhelmed during major disasters, while they are expected to be the main resources of disaster response. Learning from Japan's cases, it is said that health data registration is a necessary thing to do before disaster occurs. Moreover, Susanti & Chandra (2019) suggests that health officials such as nurses must have the competency in updating the information regarding health care access which is not limited to just the skills of treating disaster survivors. Health officials should train the community on disaster preparedness measures – thus contributing to escalate the DRR education integration processes.

5. Conclusions

The Disaster Risk Reduction Education effort in Indonesia, particularly concerning school safety has shown some dynamics on its progress. The slow integration of DRR education into education sector policy is caused by various factors, among others; lack of bottom-up initiatives, fragmented knowledge of some disaster types, the escalating risks being faced, etc. Though some progresses have been found in regards to risk reduction efforts, it is often the issues related to education and school safety need to be pushed forward, as it has been pointed out by Amri et al. (2017); Sheffield et al. (2017); Suppasari et al. (2015); Wegscheider, (2011); and Hermon et al. (2019).

Regarding school safety pillars, the Pillar 1 that covers safe learning facilities in Indonesia has been concluded to be not ready and has the least amount of progress among the three pillars. Some of the factors supporting this conclusion are the experts' observation based on the collapse of school building in past disasters, lack of disasters' safety standards, and lack of monitoring processes. Massive damages that school buildings received might have been the result of lacking building codes or safety standards against disasters. This has been strengthened by the fact that there is only an earthquake safety standard for constructing new school buildings since 2011. Apart from the absence of other disaster type safety, most of the schools constructed in the past are based on the uniformity that did not consider local disaster risks. Moreover, implementing the earthquake safety standard in newly built schools have faced with numerous challenges, including massive school numbers, geographical location, and lack coordination with local government. Besides that, an insufficient monitoring system has contributed to the obstacles. In order to overcome this issue, the central government has been developing the monitoring and evaluation platforms to better assess school safety readiness in Indonesia.

In terms of Pillar 2 (School Disaster Management), it has been arguably the most progressive school safety pillar being addressed in Indonesia, according to the expert interviews. This is mainly due to the enhanced level of stakeholder partnerships in recent years. Though the initiative in school safety is said to begun since 2006, the progress was considerably slow up to this day in terms of actualisation. The Indonesian government began to campaign about safe school in 2010, then two years later in 2012 it had just been regulated through *Peraturan Kepala BNPB No. 4 Tahun 2012* which regulate the school safety towards disasters. Meanwhile, the National Secretariat of Education Safety Unit (SPAB) was founded in 2017 comprised of various institutions including the Ministry of Education and Culture, BNPB, UNICEF, Safe the Children, and others. Moreover, the regulation had been strengthened by the Ministry of Education and Culture through *Permendikbud No. 33 Tahun 2019* that comprehensively provides a clear guidance for stakeholders from national to local level in implementing the country's school safety initiative (SPAB). Along with the long processes that seem to reveal the real progress, implementation can be challenging for the coming future. The vast amount of schools in a geographically dispersed archipelago is one to be overcome. Moreover, the role of regional and local stakeholders include government and political leaders is frequently highlighted for being significant influencers. Considering the vital roles of these, committed local leaders can escalate the implementation process while the uncommitted local actors are often found to cause a bottle neck effect.

The third pillar has similarly been portrayed as significantly progressive – taking into account the adaptability of the national curriculum. It is said that the lack of DRR contents in the curriculum should not be hampering teachers to teach students the knowledge. Instead, the curriculum offers high-flexibility in which DRR topics can be incorporated into any subject through relevant basic competency themes. The incorporation, however, will be highly dependent on the school-level stakeholders such as teachers and headmasters. Given this condition, the curriculum has actually no issues in regards of its position to adopt DRR materials for students to learn, it has something more to do with the decision makers whether they are willing to consider the adoption based on the school needs. One thing that some of the experts on this study often found doubtful is that the curriculum has not been able to position DRR education systematically – meaning that it still weighs the knowledge-based learning over more action-oriented and practical skills development. This is something that every education actor must pay attention to for making the students more attached to what they receive in DRR teaching and to practise it in their daily life so that they will always be conscious of their knowledge and skills, resulting in more resilience in coping with future disasters.

Furthermore, the teachers survey on their views concerning the three school safety pillars against haze in their respective schools seem to agree with the experts' view on some points, particularly regarding the Pillar 1 (Safe Learning Facilities) for making the least progress. From the Likert-type questions – ranging from 1 (very bad) to 5 (very good) assessing some indicators of three school safety pillars – 120 teachers across 6 haze affected provinces responded and give their view. The results reveal that Pillar 1 (safe learning facilities) receives the lowest score with the average of 3.32 followed by Pillar 2 (school disaster management) with 3.42 and the most progressive according to teacher's perspective is the Pillar 3 (risk reduction and resilience education) with the average score of 3.76. These results further strengthen the experts interview results. The total average of the score in all three pillars is 3.49 that can be considered in the middle or neither good nor bad category.

The result from both experts' interviews and the teachers' survey may suggest that there are some progresses happening in the Indonesian schools regarding school safety issues. It has been reflected by some of the positive trends discussed in the previous sections. But most importantly, there are also considerably huge barriers that need to be overcome. The assessment result to the Indonesian schools seem not to be very bad, though it has not been considered as sufficient either. However, it is clearly seen that whether the experts or teachers found that there will be more progress to come in the near future, one of the determinant factors could be whether the relevant key actors, particularly at local level are able to keep optimising the optimistic momentum going on at the national level.

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